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Научная статья

ВЛИЯНИЕ КОНФУЦИАНСТВА НА ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ СИСТЕМЫ СОЦИАЛЬНО-ФИЛОСОФСКИХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ ЦЗЭН ГО-ФАНЯ

THE INFLUENCE OF CONFUCIANISM ON FORMATION ZENG GUO- FAN'S SYSTEM OF SOCIAL, PHILOSOPHICAL VIEWS

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Статья посвящена рассмотрению категориального и понятийного аппарата философской, социальной системы Цзэн Го-фаня. В статье представлен анализ наиболее значимых категорий конфуцианства, таких как человечность, мудрость, сознание/сердце, почтение, искренность, великодушие. Сделан вывод, что значительную роль в формировании и развитии философской системы взглядов Цзэн Го-фаня сыграло неоконфуцианство, а именно “учение о сердце”, которое мыслитель анализировал через призму своего практического жизненного опыта.

The article is devoted to the consideration of the categorical and conceptual apparatus of Tseng Guofan's philosophical and social system. The article presents an analysis of the most significant categories of Confucianism, such as humanity, wisdom, consciousness/heart, reverence, sincerity, generosity. It is concluded that neo-Confucianism, namely the “doctrine of the heart”, which the thinker analyzed through the prism of his practical life experience, played a significant role in the formation and development of Tseng Guofan's philosophical system of views.

Ключевые слова: Цзэн Гофань, конфуцианство, история Китая, неоконфуцианство, философская система взглядов.

Key words: Zeng Guofan, Confucianism, Chinese history, neo-Confucianism, philosophical system of views.

In the Chinese historiographical tradition, Zeng Guofan holds a significant place as a thinker and philosopher, rather than merely as a suppressor of the Taiping Rebellion and a political figure. In contrast, the Russian-language tradition continues to predominantly portray him as an official and military leader. The philosophical ideas of Zeng Guofan (1811-1872) are undoubtedly rooted in Confucianism. Raised in a traditional Chinese family, he was raised with the principles of filial piety (xiao) and benevolence (ren), as well as a sense of responsibility for and assistance to his junior siblings. The few known facts about his youth suggest that he received a traditional upbringing, and consequently, his worldview was shaped under the influence of Confucian teachings [2, p. 372].

Little is known about his parents; there are only mentions indicating that his father was a scholar. Zeng Guofan had several brothers – Zeng Guoyan (born 1820), Zeng Guohua (born 1822),

Zeng Guoquan (born 1824), and Zeng Guobao (born 1828). Together with his brothers, he was raised in the Confucian tradition and received a corresponding classical education and upbringing [2, p. 372].

In 1833, Zeng Guofan obtained the xiucai degree, followed by the juren (舉人) degree in 1834 and the jinshi degree in 1838 [2, p. 372]. As the top-ranked candidate (shi jishi), he was appointed to the Hanlin Academy. This remarkable rise in his career reflects his extensive preparation, sharp intellect, unwavering willpower, and profound knowledge of the Confucian classical canons (Wu Jing). During this period, Zeng Guofan developed a deep interest in Song-era Confucianism, studying the teachings of Zhu Xi (1130-1200), and later, those of the Ming philosopher Wang Yangming (1472-1529) [2, p. 375]. In the Russian-language historiographical tradition, Zeng Guofan's work as a thinker and philosopher is most comprehensively explored in the dissertations of T. G. Shestakova, "The Concept of Historical Development in Confucianism of China in the Second Half of the 19th – Early 20th Century (Zeng Guofan, Zhang Zhidong)" [5, p. 98], and E.A. Vasilieva, "The Philosophical and Socio-Political Views of Zeng Guofan (1811-1872)" [8, p. 25]. There are also occasional references to Zeng Guofan as a Confucian philosopher in the context of other studies. For instance, A.I. Kobzev characterizes him as "a pillar of official Confucianism, a high-ranking official, and scholar of the Hanlin Academy" [3, p. 256].

In the Chinese tradition, a vast number of works are dedicated to various aspects of Zeng Guofan's activities, including his philosophical views and the influence of Confucianism on the formation of his worldview. Scholars such as Sun Qingbo [6], Sun Penghui [7] and others have extensively examined these topics. Their research leaves no doubt that while Zeng Guofan's philosophical system, rooted in Confucian teachings and their fundamental values, incorporates certain elements from Buddhism and Daoism, Confucianism remains its core foundation. To researchers of his life and work, particularly Zhang Minlin, Zeng Guofan's philosophical ideas offer a unique interpretation and cannot be equated with the classical interpretations of Han and Song philosophers [9, p. 5-6].

Sun Penghui wrote: "The classical Confucian philosophy, transmitted from generation to generation for thousands of years, is more deeply reflected and applied in Zeng Guofan's concepts. This became an important platform for his brilliant career" [7, p. 161]. Sun Qingbo characterizes Zeng Guofan as a model of success and an example to follow, embodying Confucian ethics and duty [6, p. 63].

At the core of Confucian teaching is the junzi (君子), the noble man, whose set of virtues every educated and well-mannered individual should aspire to cultivate. Among these virtues are ren (仁, benevolence), zhi (智, wisdom), xiao (孝, filial piety), yi (義, righteousness), xin (心, conscientious) and others [1, p. 455]. As a true Confucian, Zeng Guofan placed the individual – the noble man – at the centre of his philosophical system. He believed that one must engage in constant self-improvement, develop personal virtues, learn to manage emotions and feelings, control one's behaviour, and build proper relationships with the external world. According to this perspective, the character of each individual determines the well-being of their family and, consequently, the stability of the state and society as a whole. It is important to note that, as a pragmatist, Zeng Guofan also integrated military organization and service into this framework. However, let us return to the starting point of this logical sequence, where the noble man stands at the forefront.

Zeng Guofan outlined several key principles aligned with Confucian values, which, when followed, enable individuals to achieve self-improvement:

- 1) Maintain external decorum and respectfulness (jing, 敬). Clothing should be neat and tidy, speech should be calm, and behavior should be modest and composed.
- 2) Practice meditation or "quiet sitting" (jing zuo, 静坐). Regardless of circumstances, one should set aside time each day to be alone and reflect.

- 3) Wake up early in the morning (zao qi, 早起).
- 4) Read in an orderly manner (du shu bu er, 读书不二). One should not start a new book before finishing the previous one.
- 5) Read historical texts (du shi, 读史).
- 6) Speak thoughtfully and attentively (jin yan, 谨言).
- 7) Cultivate willpower and strengthen the spirit (yang qi, 养气).
- 8) Take care of the body (bao shen, 保身). Moderation in work, desires, and food intake is essential. One should consistently strengthen the body and prevent illness.
- 9) Strive for new knowledge (zhi zhi qi suo wang, 知致其所往).
- 10) Never be idle and continuously improve one's skills (yue wu wang suo neng, 月无忘所能).
- 11) Write poetry every month. This practice helps one understand oneself, transforming weakness into strength. One should not become a slave to desires or material possessions.
- 12) Practice calligraphy (zuo zi, 作字). This principle not only emphasizes the importance of calligraphy as an art but also carries a deeper meaning: do not postpone until tomorrow what can be done today. As tasks accumulate over time, handling them will only become more difficult. In essence, it is crucial to manage time wisely.
- 13) Avoid going out at night (ye bu chu men, 夜不出门). Set urgent matters aside and rest.
- 14) Keep a journal (xie ri ji, 写日记). Record daily experiences in detail, analyzing and reflecting on mistakes continuously. Human errors were categorised into three main areas: body (shen, 身) – physical actions, speech (kou, 口) – verbal expression, and heart (xin, 心) – emotions [9, p. 5-6].

Zeng Guofan's philosophical views are anthropocentric, with fundamental principles formulated for the individual and based on personal needs. It can be assumed that among the thirteen points related to self-improvement and the cultivation of the qualities of a noble man, some represent the thinker's unique interpretations – such as "avoiding going out at night" and "waking up early in the morning." In addition to Confucian ideas aligned with concepts like "wisdom", "benevolence", "adherence to proper conduct and etiquette", and "the pursuit of new knowledge", the influence of Daoism and Buddhism is also evident in principles such as "practicing meditation" and "cultivating willpower"

At the core of the categorical and conceptual framework of Zeng Guofan's philosophical system lie fundamental Confucian categories and concepts, which serve as the foundation for the formulation of his ideas. Let us now examine some of these concepts.

Zeng Guofan persistently returned to interpretations of the concept of "wisdom" (nei sheng) in his reflections. "Wisdom" is closely associated with the concept of "knowledge" and, in a broader sense, with the notion of "education." Zeng Guofan proposed daily practices beneficial for enhancing one's level of education: reading (看, kan), memorizing (读, du), writing (写, xie), and interpretation (作, zuo) [4, p. 203].

According to Zeng Guofan, the essence of the category of "sincerity" lies in the ability to "focus wholeheartedly on a single task" (专心存一, zhuān xīn cún yī). The thinker maintained that, in Confucianism, the ideal noble man is one who dedicates himself fully to a single pursuit. Zeng Guofan also introduced an alternative interpretation of the concept of "sincerity," asserting that "sincerity is precisely honesty (truthfulness)" (cheng bian shi zhong xin) [9, p. 3].

In Chinese philosophy, magnanimity (恕, shu) is paired with loyalty (忠, zhōng), with one of its earliest mentions appearing in the Lunyu (Analects), where the role of loyalty is to inspire others to act with sincerity, while magnanimity embodies the fundamental life principle: "Treat others as you wish to be treated". In Zeng Guofan's philosophical system, the dichotomy of these two con-

cepts serves as a means of realizing ren (仁, ren), or humanity, as a continuation of the traditional Confucian interpretation. Over time, Zeng Guofan placed primary emphasis on magnanimity, positioning respectfulness (敬, jing) above loyalty. He emphasises the importance of an individual's loyalty to oneself, one's family, the military, and the state; however, he argued that without reverence and respect, it is impossible to cultivate loyalty and magnanimity at the proper level [4, p. 207].

In the philosophical system developed by Zeng Guofan, structured as a sequential chain of interactions "individual-family-army-state" – the individual and their characteristics serve as the fundamental and structuring elements. In addition to the concepts mentioned above, particular attention must be given to another category, arguably the most significant within the thinker's entire value system: the category of "heart/mind" (心, xin). Zeng Guofan filtered all definitions and assertions through the lens of interpretations associated with the concept of xin.

The notion of xin first appeared in Western Zhou ritual texts, where it describes a state through which one can recognize, describe, comprehend, and evaluate external objects or phenomena. In Chinese culture, the category of xin reflects both the mental and psychological dimensions of an individual's personality. As early as the Da Xue, it was noted that the functioning of the sensory organs depends on the activity of the heart.

The category of xin underwent extensive development in its interpretations within Neo-Confucianism (xin ru jia). It was during this period that the leading figures of the revised Confucian tradition identified the essential characteristics of consciousness (xin): sincerity (cheng), emptiness (xu), and humanity (ren) [10, p. 81].

Zeng Guofan took into account the ideas and reflections of key Neo-Confucian thinkers. According to Zhu Xi (1130-1200), who formulated the foundational principles of the "Teaching of Principle" (lixue, 理學), the category of xin, as an individual's personal consciousness, consisted of two interconnected components: human nature (xing, 性) which is given at birth, and emotions and feelings (qingyu, 情欲) which arise as an individual interacts with the external world and experiences its influences [10, p. 81].

One of the key figures of Ming-era Confucianism, Wang Yangming (王陽明, 1472-1529), wrote that "the investigation of things should be carried out within one's own heart". Zeng Guofan deeply respected and admired the intellectual depth and scope of Wang Yangming, believing that he had succeeded in creating a new atmosphere within Confucianism [3, p. 54]. Wang Yangming's fundamental idea of "investigating things within one's own heart" is further clarified by the assertion that "the heart is principle" (xin ji li, 心即理), meaning that principle (li, 理) is inherently present within every individual's psyche. According to Wang Yangming, principles do not exist outside the heart; rather, by looking within, each person can discern good from evil, right from wrong. The "principles" that are to be uncovered through the process of "investigating things" should be sought within the subject himself, rather than in an external world [3, p. 54]. This perspective significantly altered traditional conceptions of consciousness.

Subsequently, Zhu Xi interpreted the examination of things through moral issues, while Wang Yang-ming proposed to consult the heart and pass everything through it (心, xin) [1, p. 455]. These ideas align with one of the fundamental principles of Chinese philosophy «completing the process of gaining knowledge involves thoroughly examining things».

In fact, Neo-Confucianism interprets the concept of active knowledge as an opportunity to develop the ability for intuitive comprehension of truth, and Zeng Guofan follows it and emphasizes the importance of "sincerity of intentions" and "vigour in the execution of actions" [4, p. 208].

Neo-Confucianism became a logical step in the development of Confucianism, forming its conceptual content, after which its structure was finally formed. The ethical and moral components of human nature not only emphasized the significance and importance of the individual's social sta-

tus, traditional social values (respect for parents, observance of hierarchy, continuation of traditions), but also placed the individual at the head of the entire social system. Thus, in the Confucian tradition, the category of xin is associated precisely with descriptions of human behaviour in society.

The fundamental concepts of Zeng Guofan's philosophical system are traditional categories of Confucianism (humanity, respectfulness, sincerity), which aim to correlate all aspects of a person's personality – physiological, emotional, psychological, intellectual, and ethical. The methods of self-improvement and relentless work on oneself form the basis of Zeng Guofan's reflections on the problems of transformation of an individual and the search for one's own place in society. His analysis relies on the interpretation of key categories: heart/consciousness, wisdom, including the search for a way out of the disputes between Song and Han Confucianism, as well as the interpretation of the ideas of Ming Confucianism, with the involvement of unique practical solutions. Thus, Zeng Guofan's ideas are anthropocentric, and his theoretical developments are based on the synthesis of the Confucian moral and ethical teachings in various periods of its development.

Zeng Guofan was an innovator and apologist of Confucianism, possessing a deep understanding of its various nuances and stages of formation and development, gained through his practical experience in governance and regular interaction with people. This individual must continually work on themselves to maintain mental fortitude, willpower, perseverance, and the ability to withstand life's difficulties, preserving dignity under any circumstances. Regardless of social status or initial position in society, such an individual can achieve unprecedented heights and results that were once unimaginable. Furthermore, adherence to Confucian norms (striving for the status of the noble man, the hierarchy in relationships between emperor and subjects, between parents and children, between husband and wife) and principles (reflection on mistakes, daily practices) will serve as the foundation for the birth and formation of a new, highly moral individual, with whom one can be assured of the well-being of their family in particular, and of the state as a whole.

Thus, Zeng Guofan's ideas are anthropocentric, and his theoretical framework relies on a synthesis of Confucian moral-ethical teachings across different periods of its development. Zeng Guofan was an innovator and advocate of Confucianism, deeply versed in its nuances and stages of formation due to his practical governance experience and regular interaction with people. Possessing strong will and character, he constantly studied and honed his skills, ultimately shaping and introducing into his philosophical system a new perspective on the individual in a rapidly changing society—one who must tirelessly work on self-improvement to maintain mental fortitude, willpower, perseverance, and the ability to withstand life's adversities. Such a person, regardless of social status or initial standing, can achieve unprecedented heights and results previously unimaginable at the outset of their journey.

Zeng Guofan's philosophical system is grounded in classical Confucian, which function as integrative mechanisms for aligning the multifaceted dimensions of human existence: physiological, cognitive and ethical. His methodology emphasizes relentless self-cultivation, posited as the linchpin for individual transformation and socio-ethical integration.

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